

Exploring Teacher Attrition in Public Schools: A Case Study of the Tshwane West District in Gauteng Province

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the article was to examine the way female principals experienced teacher attrition in their schools. The main question that this article wanted to understand was: What are the causes of teacher attrition in public schools?" The study was conducted in the Tshwane West District of Gauteng Province. The Tshwane West District is one of the fifteen districts of Gauteng Province, situated to the West of Pretoria. Qualitative approach was used, and method of data collected was through interviews. Fourteen female school principals were selected as key informants who could provide information on teacher attrition. Of the fourteen female principals, nine were primary school principals and five secondary school principals. These participants were chosen because they were likely to be knowledgeable and informative about teacher attrition. Analysis: Data was coded, and it was ensured that data that corresponded to the codes which were identified as the analysis was done. Patterns and themes emerged as the coding continued. Then interpretive paradigm was used to understand the participants experiences. It was found that the cause of teacher attrition was due to factors beyond the control of the schools such as legislation, technology, economy, retirement, dismissals, and redundancies in schools.

KEYWORDS: Retirement, resignation, dismissals, attrition, female principal

1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the article was to examine the way female principals experienced teacher attrition in their schools. The purpose of this paper was to better understand how female principals experienced teacher attrition. The study was conducted in the Tshwane West District of Gauteng Province. The Tshwane West District is one of the fifteen districts of Gauteng Province, situated to the West of Pretoria.

The teacher shortage and its spatial and temporal dimensions have been a persistent problem in the education sector for many years. It is not just a problem of a shortage of educational

resources in the education sector but also a problem of the spatial and temporal distribution of these resources, which affect student achievement and teacher attrition. The student-teacher rate could be used as a key indicator to measure the spatiotemporal disparity in teacher supply and demand [1].

Teacher shortages, and the widespread reports about teacher salaries could worsen teacher morale, and persistent student enrollment declines might be factors that discourage teacher to stay in schools. It is assumed that teacher compensation reform, could be a critical factor to minimise teacher turnover and attrition. The strategy to circumvent teacher attrition could be through an inflation-adjusted public school teachers' salary [2].

[3] found that the wellbeing of teachers is a growing concern internationally. They think that teachers' work is increasingly complex and demanding. Across many countries, teachers are experiencing unmanageable workloads, high levels of stress and demoralisation leading to unprecedented attrition. This is the case with teachers in Tshwane West District of Gauteng Province.

1.1 PURPOSE

To examine the way female principals experienced teacher attrition in their schools.

1.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

The question that was asked is "What are the causes of teacher attrition in public schools?"

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Effective educational leadership becomes a more relevant and necessary condition for developing and sustaining school improvement processes in low-performing schools serving socioeconomically disadvantaged students. It is expected that school principals would drive and sustain improvements by creating sustainable career pathways for teachers. Although leadership stretches across various stakeholders and positions in a school, the principal's leadership is crucial to initiating and controlling teacher attrition [4].

[5] found that despite the critical role of teachers, they often face a lack of appreciation, inadequate compensation, and a general undervaluation of their profession. Both a high attrition rate and lack of expertise negatively affect the educational outcomes of students [6]. Teacher attrition and mobility could result in a loss of schools' social capital, especially if experienced and competent teachers decide to leave schools and their job. When these teachers leave, social ties and networks of support collapse, which could result in loss of knowledge in schools with negative impacts on student achievement [7].

The role of principals in shaping and maintaining a healthy school culture is necessary because the lack of positive interactions, feeling undervalued, and a perceived absence of support from

school principals could lead to teacher attrition [8]. Teacher burnout because of additional tasks, such as the teaching of additional lessons with additional preparation requirements, could negatively impact teachers' wellbeing and this might lead to teacher attrition [9]. Burnout is a psychological syndrome emerging as a prolonged response to chronic interpersonal job stressors. If teachers are expected to be the agents of intervention and if those experiencing burnout are possibly doing so at low levels of fidelity, this could result in negligible, null, or even harmful effects on stakeholders in schools [10].

[8] found that public schools are faced with the challenge of a growing number of teachers choosing to leave the profession every year, leaving schools struggling to recruit and retain qualified teachers. Negative school culture contributes to teachers' job dissatisfaction, which is among the primary reasons behind teachers' decisions to leave and dissuade others from joining the profession. Relationships and interactions among teacher-student, colleagues, school leaders, and other workers in the school workplace is one of the building blocks of teacher well-being. Possessing positive social relationships among those parties can increase the quality of teachers' well-being. However, social dynamics in the workplace could cause friction among those parties. This could lead to depersonalization then causing them to experience burnout, and in some cases job attrition [11] .

Attrition is a natural occurrence within all professions. The high rates of teachers leaving the profession have economic, educational, professional, and personal consequences that cannot be ignored. When teachers leave unexpectedly, there is a disruption to students' learning and the school context more broadly in terms of social cohesion. Teachers tend to describe problematic workplace conditions in terms of 'sub-par relationships with school administrators and colleagues, feeling a lack of support by school leadership, and poor school culture and low morale, workplace bullying by parents and students could lead to teacher attrition [12].

[13] found that the teaching profession is the most stressful occupations with the potential to result in poor health because teachers are expected to endure the social and psychological effects of isolation and fear for their health due to teaching workload. They also see teachers as frontline workers risking their own health by returning to in-person education and continuing to provide instruction to students amidst the challenges of Covid-19 and other related school issues. There are different types of teacher attrition such as voluntary attrition, involuntary attrition, retirement attrition, internal attrition and demographic specific attrition. The causes of teacher attrition amongst others could be the result of low salary, poor working condition, leadership style and rural posting of teachers [14].

[15] found that there are numerous factors that contribute to teachers' decisions to leave their jobs. These may include job satisfaction, work-life balance, career advancement opportunities, organizational culture, and compensation. The lack of support from the school administration, lack of professional autonomy, and increased stress could cause teacher attrition. Attrition is a natural occurrence within all professions and can be the result of retirement, family responsibilities, relocation, mobility and health. The high rates of teachers leaving the profession have economic, educational, professional and personal consequences that cannot be ignored. As

Teacher attrition can ‘wreak havoc on students, other teachers, school administrators and the surrounding community alike [12].

[16] are of the opinion that teacher attrition is a complex issue shaped by individuals and contextual circumstances, but often reflective of the characteristics of teachers’ perceived working conditions in schools. Teachers who leave schools are dictated by the contexts in schools and they finally make their decisions to leave. Media coverage suggests that schools would be facing a critical dearth of teachers due to teacher attrition. Teachers’ mental and physical health are affected and this could drive them to leave the profession. Symptoms that teachers might display due to fatigue are headaches, insomnia, panic attacks, eating disorders, gastrointestinal issues and kidney and heart problems [16].

[17] believe that teachers are the most critical school-level variables impacting student achievement in schools. Teachers’ widespread perception of a lack of support from their school principals lead to their feelings that the schools’ working conditions made their circumstances worse. Teachers’ perceptions about their working conditions could be an overwhelming negative experience on their teaching activities. Also, teachers could experience the effects of issues related to demoralization and lack of voice in decision-making capacity when it comes to issues within the realms of their work.

Teacher attrition would always be a challenge because changes in financial incentives are always paired with other changes that may also influence exit behavior of teachers, e.g., adjustments to age and service retirement eligibility thresholds being revised. In fact, any change to eligibility thresholds will affect both the timing and the magnitude of the financial incentives teachers face. This link makes it difficult to isolate the impact of financial incentives from other pushing factors. Teachers' responsiveness to traditional pension plans and financial incentives could suffer from this issue. To overcome this challenge could be by focusing on reforms that could substantially change financial incentives that would be consistent with teachers’ retirement plans [18].

3. METHOD

This section dealt with the method used in the study.

3.1 Data collection

Qualitative approach was used, and method of data collected was through interviews and the participants experiences were interpreted relying on the interpretive paradigm. Sampling: Fourteen female school principals were selected as key informants who could provide information on teacher attrition. Of the fourteen female principals, nine were primary school principals and five secondary school principals. These participants were chosen because they were likely to be knowledgeable and informative about teacher attrition. The researchers ensured the reliability of the interviews by cross-referencing the interview data with existing literature to

ensure consistency and strengthen the credibility of the findings. By providing detailed descriptions of the context, participants, and data collection process, the researchers ensured that the findings are rich and transparent, helping future researchers to assess the reliability of the study's findings. To ensure that the interpretations of the data was accurate, the researchers shared initial findings with participants to confirm that their experiences were accurately captured and represented. To enhance reliability, the researchers used a consistent set of questions for all participants, helping to maintain focus on key themes like teacher attrition while still allowing for open-ended responses.

3.2 Data analysis

Data was coded, and it was ensured that data that corresponded to the codes which were identified as the analysis was done. Patterns and themes emerged as the coding continued. Then interpretive paradigm was used to understand the participants experiences. The interpretive paradigm helped the researchers understand how the participants make sense of their experiences. By relying on this paradigm, the researchers interpreted data within the specific cultural and social contexts of the participants, rather than imposing a pre-existing framework. This ensured that the findings are grounded in the participants' realities and not biased by external frameworks. Also, the researchers' awareness of their own biases and assumptions ensured reliability. Reflexivity involves regularly reflecting on how the researchers' own experiences or perspectives might influence the interpretation of the data. The researchers used a systematic approach to analyzing the interview data, such as coding for key themes related to teacher attrition. By identifying patterns and checking the consistency of these patterns across the interviews, the reliability of the conclusions is enhanced. To ensure that the interpretations of the data are accurate, the researchers shared initial findings with participants to confirm that their experiences were accurately captured and represented.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

There are different types of teacher attrition, for example, voluntary and involuntary teacher attrition. Teacher attrition may occur in the form of resignation, retirement, Ill-health and death, transfer and redeployment, and dismissal.

Teacher attrition may occur in the form of resignation which is classified as voluntary. In this article the term resignation will refer to the teacher when terminating their employment contract voluntarily.

4.1.1 Resignation

Data revealed that all the participants experienced teachers' attrition through resignation, as reported by participants. The pseudonyms used below are to protect the identity of the participants and the names used are not the participants' real names.

“Ohh, resignation is the most thing I have experienced”. (Doris)

“I have experienced teachers leaving the school because they wanted to do what we call withdrawal, they resigned”. (Adelaide)

“I experienced resignations because now it’s on fashion because people need to cash up their pensions”. (Mavis)

In addition, another participant said the following about resignation:

“Luckily at my school they are not really leaving the school. So, I am very thankful and privileged. I am thankful for that”. (Cathy).

Participants also indicated that teachers resign in order to have access to their pension funds to ensure that they have ready money:

I think the reason is monetary gains. They wanted to cash their pension. I think in this case, you know, educators are pressed for money. That’s what I’m thinking because I know of one who just wanted to get the pension fund, so that she can beautify her house and thereafter she went back to teaching. (Mercy)

Yes, monetary problems because all of them went back to the system except for one. But all of them raising monetary challenges. They wanted to have cash to do all these, whatever they were experiencing. It was just voluntarily. I think you know that system of teachers leaving the system for financial gain and coming back to the system also. (Gemma)

Alice explained what happened with many teachers:

It is because they wanted to get their money and come back to the system, so all of them those who resigned, and they are back in the different schools, teaching.

4.1.2 Retirement

Teachers generally retire and stop teaching when they reach the retirement age. Normal retirement in the education system in South Africa takes place in the year that a teacher turns 65, but teachers can retire as early as 55 years of age.

The data revealed that participants had teachers who left the schools due to retirement.

those were the only three who left the school through pension (retirement), (Daisy).

I think retirements are two. (Gemma).

[Laughing]. Those who went on pension I can safely say about four. (Mercy)

It is apparent from the above evidence that teachers retire because they have reached the retirement age of 65 years. There is nothing the participants can do except to let the teacher leave because the Department does not allow teacher to serve beyond retirement age. The finding aligns with the fact that compulsory retirement age is 65 years in South Africa. Optional

retirement age is from 55 years and thus teachers may take early retirement at that age. The data presented above also showed that there were no teachers who took early retirement.

4.1.3 Ill-health and death

Let me start with those who start by being sick. The participant said, “Then the person will be sick for a week, and then you know you have a hope because you can’t substitute such a teacher. Then you just substitute internally, just say okay mam so and so, Mr. so and so will be coming in but mam so and so this week she is not in then according to the doctor’s note it’s up to maybe Friday. Then you are expecting the teacher to come back on Monday, come Monday, no, another extension of another week. Then you are just waiting, what about the learners. Because you cannot, even you take teachers to say no substitute this class, substitute, it’s just a monitoring it’s not substitution per se where they are going to teach those classes”. (Victoria).

In addition to the teachers who take short sick leave, some teachers become sick for an extended time, as indicated by the participants below:

“Ohh, the last one was in 2018, she was sick for a long time. (Letia)

“the latest one that left, was ill, ehh, you know he was frequently absent because she was on PILIR (long leave)”. (Mavis)

“But at this point in time, we have a teacher who has been on sick leave since 2016 (PILIR). Ehhm thus far that’s the most worrying also had quite a number of teachers who went on sick leave, long period, sick leave. Five so far”. (Anna)

“She came to our school in 2015, and ever since, she has been on and off, on and off and in and out of the hospital”. (Kate)

When teachers have to be medically boarded due to ill-health, the Department processes the paperwork, which takes time, causing a delay that makes it difficult to find a replacement.

“I have a teacher who has been sick for a long time. I am waiting for the approval letter from the province. Letter from Gauteng province to release the teacher. So, everything, paperwork, was done but the only problem is that the province is very slow in doing things, it takes long for them to solve some other problems. So, all in all, we believe they will send that as soon as possible but I’ve been waiting”. (Hazel)

The data showed that it is not only the Department that delays the process of appointments but also the doctors of the teachers who are sick, as they take time to complete the necessary forms needed to start the process of appointing another teacher or a substitute teacher.

“In the case of long sick leave, we experience delays because doctors are giving us a hard time in getting those forms and without that form, you cannot appoint a teacher. You need to have those forms for you to submit to the district office. It’s then that they can allow you to appoint but it depends on an individual doctor, medical doctor as to how they interact with those forms”. (Fiona)

In some cases, teachers who are sick and have been on extended sick leave do not recover and pass on. This is reported by the participants below:

“I had two teachers who passed on, they were both not well”. (Fiona)

I lost two teachers in the same month on consecutive days. And all of them it was death. (Iris)

I experienced only one death case. A female teacher. She got sick just for a short time and she passed on. (Nancy)

Iris was able to disclose the cause of the passing of two teachers at her school:

All of them was death through stress. Uhhh, it was hectic. Uhhh, I didn't take it well. So, it was a difficult moment, to lose such people and then finding out afterwards that it was ehh financial stress related.

4.1.4 Transfer and Redeployment

Transfer and redeployment are some of the factors that influence teacher attrition. Transfer tends to be a voluntary action which is sought by the teachers. This is what participants said:

Ehhmmm, teachers that left the school through transfer, actually, two teachers got cross transfers, the first one is staying next to the school where she went to. (Elsa)

Ja, I just experienced one teacher who left on transfer, [silence] whom maybe ehhh, had a challenge with her peers, they did not see eye to eye and then I advised her not to resign, I then sat down with her and advised her to do a cross transfer and she agreed and left.

Fiona showed her caring nature by advising one of her teachers, who seemed to be unhappy, not to resign but to consider taking a cross transfer. This meant cross transferring with another teacher who was working in a school close to where Fiona's teacher lived, so this transfer would be a convenient one for her.

Judy had a teacher who was moved to another schools through redeployment. She explained that:

So, we actually sat with her personally and put her in excess. She was currently put to another school where there is a need for her subject.

Elsa explained that identifying only one person out of the whole staff for deployment was difficult and something she did not relish doing:

“I only experienced it once, while I have been here at this school, to declare a teacher in excess, that to me was very difficult. I lost a teacher once at this school through redeployment. It was 2011 beginning of 2012. We had to lose one teacher and that is so difficult because if you must start to think of your teachers who do you want to declare in excess. So, it's not a nice experience. But that was the first and the last time I had to declare somebody in excess I did not

appreciate that, but you know you have your SMT support to say it wasn't my decision alone we collectively came to decide that this is the teacher." (Elsa)

The above-mentioned findings are supported by [11] Fauzan et al., (2024), who found that social dynamics in the workplace could cause friction among those parties involved. This could lead to depersonalization then causing them to experience burnout, and in some cases job attrition.

4.1.5 Dismissal.

Only one participant reported having a teacher who was dismissed due to incapacity. This is how Judy explained the situation:

"Ehh, so since my appointment last year we had ehhe, one teacher who had a disciplinary hearing, ehhe, he was not performing and as a principal, what can I say, the expectations of the Department and my own, I would like the school to become the best school in this area. So ehhe, we are looking at teacher performance, so we had a hearing, and he was dismissed after a hearing.

Maria, as the principal is responsible for the quality and effectiveness of the school, had reason to dismiss a teacher due to incapacity. Dismissing a teacher in this manner must follow set procedures and there are protocols that need to be observed, as Maria further mentioned:

"Ehh, there is a few that I would like to leave, ehhe, that we are working on because for me as a principal, I want the best teacher in the class. I did not appoint them, I inherited them. They are struggling with discipline; we have done intervention. They are Gauteng Department of Education (GDE), so I also involved the district, ehhe but you know how the district works. It's you know hearing, development, another hearing so it's going to take time, but I have currently four people that I actually would like to leave but, that is a process". (Maria)

4.2 DISCUSSION

4.2.1 Resignation

Resignation refers to when the employee terminates his/her employment contract out of his/her own accord. Data revealed that all the participants experienced teachers leaving their employment through resignation, as reported by participants:

" Ohh, resignation is the most thing I have experienced ".(Yvonne).

The experience of Yvonne is real because it is supported by [18] Goldhaber et al., (2024) who found that teacher attrition would always be a challenge because changes in financial incentives would always influence exit behavior of teachers. Teachers' responsiveness to their pension plans financial incentives could suffer from this issue. To overcome this challenge could be by focusing on reforms that could change financial incentives that would be consistent with teachers' retirement plans and wishes [18].

“I have experienced teachers leaving the school because they wanted to do what we call withdrawal, they resigned”. (Alice)

“I experienced resignations because now it’s on fashion because people need to cash up their pensions” (Fiona).

The assertion by Alice is supported by [5] who found that despite the critical role of teachers, they are forced to resign to get pay-out of their pension because of inadequate compensation. Both a high attrition rate and lack of expertise negatively affect the educational outcomes of schools [6].

In addition, another participant said the following about resignation:

“Luckily at my school they are not really leaving the school. So, I am very thankful and privileged. I am thankful for that”. (Cathy).

Cathy’s response to the question showed that she regards her school as blessed because not many teachers resign and leave the school. She further regards herself and the school as being in a fortunate position regarding staffing. [15] Mishra et al., (2024) found that there are numerous factors that contribute to teachers’ decisions to leave their jobs.

In many cases, teachers resign to cash in or withdraw their pension. This may be influenced by the fact that teachers are in debt, and they need additional finances to settle their debts. One other issue might be that teachers are no longer happy in their job. When teachers are unhappy, they are likely to resign and look for something better elsewhere.

The data revealed that some of the teachers left their work because they had financial problems thus, they left their positions to cash in their pension, to attend to their financial challenges or crisis.

4.2.2 Retirement

Teachers generally retire and stop teaching when they reach the retirement age. Normal retirement in the education system in South Africa takes place in the year that a teacher turns 65, but teachers can retire as early as 55 years of age.

The data revealed that participants had teachers who left the schools due to retirement.

those were the only three who left the school through pension (retirement), (Daisy).

“I think retirements are two”. (Gemma).

[Laughing]. “Those who went on pension I can safely say about four”. (Mercy)

Attrition is a natural occurrence within all professions and can be the result of retirement, family responsibilities, relocation, mobility and health [13]. Also, [5] found that despite the critical role of teachers, they often face a lack of appreciation, inadequate compensation, and a general undervaluation of their profession.

It is apparent from the above evidence that teachers retire because they have reached the retirement age of 65 years. There is nothing the participants can do except to let the teacher leave because the Department does not allow teacher to serve beyond retirement age. The finding aligns with the fact that compulsory retirement age is 65 years in South Africa. Optional retirement age is from 55 years and thus teachers may take early retirement at that age. The data presented above also showed that there were no teachers who took early retirement.

4.2.3 Ill-health and death

“Let me start with those who start by being sick. Then the person will be sick for a week, and then you know you have a hope because you can’t substitute such a teacher. Then you just substitute internally, just say okay mam so and so, Mr. so and so will be coming in but mam so and so this week she is not in then according to the doctor’s note it’s up to maybe Friday. Then you are expecting the teacher to come back on Monday, come Monday, no, another extension of another week. Then you are just waiting, what about the learners. Because you cannot, even you take teachers to say no substitute this class, substitute, it’s just a monitoring it’s not substitution per se where they are going to teach those classes”. (Nancy).

The finding is supported by [16] Barber and Literat (2024), who are of the opinion that teacher attrition is a complex issue shaped by individuals and contextual circumstances, but often reflective of the characteristics of teachers perceived working conditions in schools.

In addition to the teachers who take short sick leave, some teachers become sick for an extended time, as indicated by the participants below:

“Ohh, the last one was in 2018, she was sick for a long time. (Nancy)

the latest one that left, was ill, ehh, you know he was frequently absent because she was on PILIR (long leave)”. (Judy)

“But at this point in time, we have a teacher who has been on sick leave since 2016 (PILIR). Ehhm thus far that’s the most worrying also had quite a number of teachers who went on sick leave, long period, sick leave. Five so far”. (Betty)

“She came to our school in 2015, and ever since, she has been on and off, on and off and in and out of the hospital”. (Fiona)

Fiona's assertion is in line with [16] who maintain that teachers’ mental and physical health are affected and this could drive them to leave the profession.

When teachers have to be medically boarded due to ill-health, the Department processes the paperwork, which takes time, causing a delay that makes it difficult to find a replacement.

“I have a teacher who has been sick for a long time. I am waiting for the approval letter from the province. Letter from Gauteng province to release the teacher. So, everything, paperwork, was done but the only problem is that the province is very slow in doing things, it takes long for them

to solve some other problems. So, all in all, we believe they will send that as soon as possible but I've been waiting". (Hazel)

The data showed that it is not only the Department that delays the process of appointments but also the doctors of the teachers who are sick, as they take time to complete the necessary forms needed to start the process of appointing another teacher or a substitute teacher.

In the case of long sick leave, we experience delays because doctors are giving us a hard time in getting those forms and without that form, you cannot appoint a teacher. You need to have those forms for you to submit to the District office. It's then that they can allow you to appoint but it depends on an individual doctor, medical doctor as to how they interact with those forms. (Fiona)

In some cases, teachers who are sick and have been on extended sick leave do not recover and pass on. This is reported by the participants below:

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"I lost two teachers in the same month on consecutive days. And all of them it was death". (Iris)

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Iris was able to disclose the cause of the passing of two teachers at her school:

All of them was death through stress. Uhhh, it was hectic. Uhhh, I didn't take it well. So, it was a difficult moment, to lose such people and then finding out afterwards that it was ehh stress related.

4.2.4 Transfer and Redeployment

Transfer and redeployment are some of the factors that influence teacher attrition. Transfer tends to be a voluntary action which is sought by the teachers. This is what participants said:

"Ehhmmm, teachers that left the school through transfer, actually, two teachers got cross transfers, the first one is staying next to the school where she went to. (Elsa)"; "Ja, I just experienced one teacher who left on transfer, [silence] whom maybe ehhh, had a challenge with her peers, they did not see eye to eye and then I advised her not to resign, I then sat down with her and advised her to do a cross transfer and she agreed and left". (Fiona)

Fiona showed her caring nature by advising one of her teachers, who seemed to be unhappy, not to resign but to consider taking a cross transfer. This meant cross transferring with another teacher who was working in a school close to where Fiona's teacher lived, so this transfer would be a convenient one for her.

Judy had a teacher who was moved to another schools through redeployment. She explained that:

So, we actually sat with her personally and put her in excess. She was currently put to another school where there is a need for her subject.

Emile explained that identifying only one person out of the whole staff for deployment was difficult and something she did not relish doing:

“I only experienced it once, while I have been here at this school, to declare a teacher in excess, that to me was very difficult. I lost a teacher once at this school through redeployment. It was 2011 beginning of 2012. We had to lose one teacher and that is so difficult because if you must start to think of your teachers who do you want to declare in excess. So, it’s not a nice experience. But that was the first and the last time I had to declare somebody in excess I did not appreciate that, but you know you have your SMT support to say it wasn’t my decision alone we collectively came to decide that this is the teacher” (Emile). The above-mentioned findings are supported by [11] Marino (2024), who found that public schools are faced with the challenge of a growing number of teachers choosing to leave the profession every year, leaving schools struggling to recruit and retain qualified teachers.

4.2.5 Dismissal

Only one participant reported having a teacher who was dismissed due to incapacity. This is how Judy explained the situation:

“Ehh, so since my appointment last year we had ehhh, one teacher who had a disciplinary hearing, ehh, he was not performing and as a principal, what can I say, the expectations of the Department and my own, I would like the school to become the best school in this area. So ehh, we are looking at teacher performance, so we had a hearing, and he was dismissed after a hearing. Teachers’ mental and physical health are affected, and this could drive them to leave the profession” (Cathy). For example, this assertion by Cathy is supported by [17], who found that the symptoms that teachers might display due to fatigue are headaches, insomnia, panic attacks, eating disorders, gastrointestinal issues and kidney and heart problems.

Judy, as the principal is responsible for the quality and effectiveness of the school, had reason to dismiss a teacher due to incapacity. Dismissing a teacher in this manner must follow set procedures and there are protocols that need to be observed, as Judy further mentioned:

Ehh, there is a few that I would like to leave, ehh, that we are working on because for me as a principal, I want the best teacher in the class. I did not appoint them, I inherited them. They are struggling with discipline; we have done intervention. They are Gauteng Department of Education (GDE), so I also involved the district, ehh but you know how the district works. It’s you know hearing, development, another hearing so it’s going to take time, but I have currently four people that I actually would like to leave but, that is a process. The above-mentioned findings are supported by [1] Wu and Zhang (2024), who found that the student-teacher rate could be used as a key indicator to measure the spatiotemporal disparity in teacher supply and demand.

5. IMPLICATIONS FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

5.1 Resignation and Financial Considerations

The frequent occurrence of teacher resignations, often driven by financial factors such as accessing pension funds, suggests the need for better financial support structures for teachers. Policies could be developed to address the financial stresses that lead to voluntary resignation, ensuring teachers feel more secure in their roles. This could include initiatives like better retirement planning, salary reviews, or financial literacy programs to help teachers manage their finances without feeling compelled to resign for financial gain.

5.2 Retirement and Age-Related Attrition

The retirement age policy, set at 65, contributes to teacher attrition, with some teachers retiring earlier. While this is a natural part of workforce turnover, it may lead to a shortage of experienced teachers. Education authorities could consider developing mentorship programs to bridge the gap between retiring teachers and newer recruits, ensuring knowledge transfer. Additionally, providing incentives for older teachers to remain in the workforce longer could help mitigate the loss of experienced educators.

5.3 Ill-Health and Its Impact on Teacher Availability

Extended sick leave, often due to chronic illness, is another factor influencing teacher attrition. The delays caused by the administrative process of approving sick leave and medical boarding suggest that the education system may benefit from streamlining these procedures to ensure a quicker response in replacing absent teachers. Furthermore, offering better support for teachers' health and well-being, including mental health services, could reduce the frequency and duration of long-term sick leave.

5.4 Death and Stress

Teacher deaths, often related to stress, point to the need for better support systems in place to address mental health and work-life balance. The education sector could prioritize programs that focus on stress management and resilience training for teachers. Additionally, the system should ensure that schools are equipped with appropriate bereavement support for affected colleagues.

5.5 Transfers, Redeployment, and Job Satisfaction

Teacher transfers, whether voluntary or as a result of redeployment, suggest that school dynamics and interpersonal relationships can influence teacher retention. Addressing issues related to workplace culture, peer relationships, and conflict management could reduce the

number of transfers or resignations due to dissatisfaction. Principals and school management teams could implement conflict resolution programs or peer support networks to foster a more positive working environment.

5.6 Dismissal for Incapacity

Dismissal due to incapacity, while rare, underlines the importance of clear performance management policies. It is essential for schools to have robust teacher evaluation systems that provide support for underperforming teachers through professional development, mentoring, and improvement plans before resorting to dismissal. Principals and school management should ensure that disciplinary processes are fair and transparent, with adequate support structures for teachers facing difficulties.

5.7 Policy Recommendations

Financial Support: Introduce financial literacy programs, improved retirement planning, and salary reviews to prevent financial stress-driven resignations of teachers. **Health and Well-Being:** There should be programs focusing on mental and physical health support, including stress management and wellness initiatives for teachers. **Workplace Culture:** There should be a fostering of a positive school environment through conflict resolution training, peer support, and professional development to enhance job satisfaction and reduce voluntary attrition. **Streamlining Processes:** There should be a simplification of administrative processes related to sick leave, medical boarding, and teacher replacements to minimize delays. **Retirement Support:** Again, there must be a development of mentorship programs to ensure knowledge transfer from retiring teachers and consider offering incentives for older teachers to stay longer. **Performance Management:** Also, there should be a strengthening of performance evaluation systems by providing clear pathways for underperforming teachers to improve before considering dismissal. These strategies can help reduce teacher attrition and create a more stable and supportive educational environment for both teachers and students.

6. CONCLUSION

Teacher attrition in public schools is a significant and growing issue that many educational institutions are struggling to address. The departure of teachers from the profession has long-term consequences for students, schools, and entire education systems. There are a variety of factors contributing to this challenge, some of which lie beyond the control of individual schools or school districts. One of the primary causes of teacher attrition is legislation. Laws and policies surrounding education funding, teacher evaluations, and standardized testing often create pressures that can push teachers out of the profession. For example, standardized testing and accountability measures can result in stressful work environments for educators, leading to burnout and dissatisfaction. Additionally, legislative changes that affect pensions, salaries, and

job security may prompt teachers to seek work elsewhere. Another important factor is technology. While technological advancements offer many opportunities for improving education, they can also be a source of frustration for teachers. The rapid pace of technological change can be overwhelming, especially for those who feel unprepared to integrate new tools into their classrooms. Moreover, the increased emphasis on technology in education can contribute to feelings of isolation for teachers, as they may struggle to balance traditional teaching methods with digital platforms.

The economy also plays a significant role in teacher attrition. Budget cuts, funding shortages, and economic instability can lead to layoffs, reduced salaries, and limited resources for teachers. These financial challenges often result in increased workloads and fewer support systems for educators, which can be a major contributing factor to teachers leaving the profession. Furthermore, teachers may be attracted to other, more financially stable career options that offer better compensation and benefits. Retirement is another factor contributing to teacher attrition. As many educators approach retirement age, they may choose to leave the profession after years of service. This generational shift can result in a loss of experienced and knowledgeable teachers, leading to a gap in the workforce that is difficult to fill. While retirement is often voluntary, its impact on the overall teacher workforce can be significant, especially when a large portion of the teaching staff is nearing retirement. In addition to these systemic factors, teachers may also face dismissals or redundancies due to various reasons, including poor performance evaluations or school restructurings. While dismissals can occur for legitimate reasons, they can also contribute to teacher dissatisfaction and disillusionment with the profession. Similarly, redundancies often occur because of declining student enrollment or changes in educational priorities, further exacerbating the challenge of teacher retention. One of the most critical consequences of teacher attrition is the loss of a school's social capital. Schools rely heavily on experienced and competent educators who contribute to the development of a positive school culture, mentor younger teachers, and create meaningful relationships with students. When experienced teachers leave, schools lose this valuable social capital, which can affect the overall quality of education. Furthermore, high turnover rates can create instability within schools, making it difficult for students to form strong connections with teachers and reducing the continuity of instruction.

Teacher attrition and mobility also create additional challenges for students, particularly those in underfunded or high-poverty schools. These schools often face greater difficulties in recruiting and retaining qualified educators, leading to a cycle of instability that negatively impacts student outcomes. When teachers leave, students may face disruptions in their education, resulting in a lack of continuity in instruction and decreased academic performance. In conclusion, teacher attrition is a multifaceted issue that requires a comprehensive understanding of the various factors at play. Addressing the root causes of teacher attrition requires collaboration between policymakers, school leaders, and communities to create supportive and sustainable working environments for educators. By recognizing and mitigating the factors that contribute to teacher turnover, schools can better retain their most asset: their teachers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wu, X., & Zhang, J. (2024). Case Study on Spatial Mismatch between Multivariate and Student-Teacher Rate in US Public School Districts. *Social Sciences*, 13(2), 93. <http://doi.org/10.3390/socsci13020093>
- [2] Cameron -Anglum, J., Manion, A., & Varkey, S. (2024). Increasing Minimum Teacher Salaries: Opportunities and Drawbacks Across Geography and Race. *Urban Affairs Review*, 10780874241237412. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10780874241237412>
- [3] Karnovsky, S., & Gobby, B. (2024). How teacher wellbeing can be cruel: refusing discourses of wellbeing in an online Reddit forum. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 1-19. <http://10.1080/01425692.2024.2312805>
- [4] Kuzmanic, D., Valenzuela, J. P., Montecinos, C., Allende, C., & Vanni, X. (2024). What Happens Next? Unraveling Career Trajectories After Becoming a Principal in Chile's Primary Schools. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2024.2324441>
- [5] Rocque, S. R., Goswami, R., & Malhotra, N. (2024). Towards a Better Understanding of Teacher Recognition in Society: Issues and Challenges. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 7(1), 19-24. <https://doi.org/10.47814/ijssrr.v7i1.1782>
- [6] Barnett, E., & Huang, T. (2024). Increasing Teacher Retention and Supporting Students With Low-Incidence Disabilities Through University Partnership. *Rural Special Education Quarterly*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/87568705241232388>
- [7] Van Eycken, L., Amitai, A., & Van Houtte, M. (2024). Be true to your school? Teachers' turnover intentions: The role of socioeconomic composition, teachability perceptions, emotional exhaustion and teacher efficacy. *Research Papers in Education*, 39(1), 24-49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2022.2089208>
- [8] Marino, M. T. (2024). Honoring Teacher Voice, Thoughts, and Opinions: The Impact of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Retention (Doctoral dissertation, Youngstown State University). http://rave.ohiolink.edu/etdc/view?acc_num=ysu1707639888900266
- [9] Selland, B. (2024). Understanding the Experiences of Teachers Returning to In-Person Teaching with Additional Responsibilities: A Generic Qualitative Inquiry (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University).

- [10] Deger, G. K., Moohr, M., Riden, B., & Taylor, J. (2024). Behavior, Paperwork, Instruction, & Supervision. . . Oh My!: A Review of the Literature on Mentorship for Teachers of Children With EBD. *Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorders*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/10634266241235131>
- [11] Fauzan, Z., Drajadi, N. A., & Putra, K. A. (2024). Exploring Depersonalization Toll on EFL Teachers' Well-Being in Social Contexts. *Project (Professional Journal of English Education)*, 7(1), 230-237. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4451-3778>
- [12] [12] Brandenburg, R., Larsen, E., Simpson, A., Sallis, R., & Trần, D. (2024). 'I left the teaching profession... and this is what I am doing now': a national study of teacher attrition. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-024-00697-1> [13]
- [13] Devers, K., Duyar, I., & Buchanan, K. (2024). Examining Teacher Attrition through the Experiences of Former Teachers before and during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Education Sciences*, 14(2), 184. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14020184> Educational Researcher, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-024-00697-1>
- [14] Ineye-Briggs, C. A. (2024). Teacher Attrition and Students' Academic Performance in Private Secondary Schools in Rivers State: Implications for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*, 31(4), 134-143. <https://journals.journalsplace.org/index.php/JEDA>
- [15] Mishra, T. K., Latha, C. M., Malhotra, P., Sathya, P., Gomathi, S., & Padma, S. (2024). The Impact of Job Attrition And Understanding The Factors Affecting Attrition And Intention: A Theoretical Framework. *Migration Letters*, 21(S1), 953-961. www.migrationletters.com
- [16] Barber, C., & Literat, I. (2024). TikTok as a lens into teacher attrition: perspectives from# teacherquittok. *English Teaching: Practice & Critique*. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/1175-8708.htm>
- [17] Nerlino, E. (2024). 'Beyond Frustrated': Teachers Perception of State Educational Agency Policy During the Pandemic-Impacted 2020-2021 School Year. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2024.2313002>
- [18] Goldhaber, D., Grout, C., Holden, K. L., & McGee, J. B. (2024). Evidence on the Relationship between Pension-Driven Financial Incentives and Late-Career Attrition: Implications for Pension Reform. *ILR Review*, 77(2), 175-198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00197939231221>